

Project:
ISABEL
 (Grand Agreement 691752)

***"Triggering Sustainable Biogas Energy Communities
 through Social Innovation"***

Funding Scheme: Coordination and Support Action

Programme: HORIZON2020

Societal Challenge: "Secure, clean and efficient energy"

D6.1: ISABEL Social Media Accounts

Issued by:	WHITE RESEARCH
Issue date:	29/01/2016
Due date:	31/01/2016
Work Package Leader:	WHITE RESEARCH

Start date of project: 01 January 2016

Duration: 36 months

Document History (Revisions – Amendments)	
Version and date	Changes
1.0. – 30/01/2016	First Version

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
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1. Introduction – scope of the document

This report aims to set an operational framework for the project's Social Media Accounts (SMAs). It outlines and justifies the strategic choices in the design and operation of the project's social media accounts. More specifically, it clarifies what these accounts are, what are the target audiences, what material/message they intend to communicate, how they will be used and by whom, how and what will the users contribute. This report therefore outlines the SMAs structure and function, specifies their content, clarifies the project partners' contribution and role in maintaining and updating them, and describes how they will help in delivering the project's key messages to specific target audiences.

The SMAs are functioning in the context of the wider communication strategy of the project. They have a central role in the promotion, communication, awareness creation and stakeholders' engagement activities of the partners. They also contribute in the development of the local biogas communities, a core objective of the project. **The goal is to create and maintain an active online community of supporters and followers** that will ultimately evolve to catalyse its own growth, become partly autonomous, and continue to exist beyond the duration of the project. Although there is no strategy that can guarantee this outcome, the chances of this happening are maximised if:

- ✓ the SMAs deployed are complementary and communicate specific messages (i.e. type of content) to a well-defined target audience;
- ✓ the distinctions and inter-relation in-between the SMAs, the project activities, and the other digital tools (i.e. portal, apps, etc.) are clear (see to the figure below); and
- ✓ the SMAs are kept alive and continuously fed with material in order to communicate a vibrant and active community.

This document describes how these will play out in each and every SMA that will be used in the context of this project.

Figure 1: The Social Media in the context of ISABEL's Communication and Awareness Strategy

2. SMA bouquet as a whole

2.1 Key messages

In order for the SMAs to be effective, the key messages that will be communicated through them must be clarified. These should coincide with the core concepts of the project which should, taken all together, represent the main vision of ISABEL. The core messages that ISABEL advocates can therefore be stated as follows:

- (i) A transition towards sustainable bioenergy
- (ii) Sustainable Bioenergy as a Public Good (Commons)
- (iii) AD Biogas from organic waste as a paradigmatic case of sustainable bioenergy
- (iv) The Community Energy model as a necessary condition for sustainable AD Biogas systems

Important note: in order to fulfil the project's ambitions and claims, the above concepts/messages must be communicated in concert and not in isolation.

2.2 Role of partners/consortium

The team members of the consortium will play a key role in providing content for the SMAs. Part of this content will be a natural by-product of the project's progress as most activities, outcomes, milestones, and progress will be communicated through the SMAs. However, partners will also be required to submit specific contributions. They are expected to help maintain the activity in the Social Media through posts, material, and initiate and participate in discussions. In general, the consortium partners will bring the following dimensions to the SMAs:

- (i) **Localisation:** The regional partners will provide the link with each region. They will upload posts on local developments (in direct or indirect relation to the project), events, engagement activities, milestones, etc. Moreover, the national coordinators will also focus more on the national level reporting on higher-level developments (e.g. changes in relevant national policies).
- (ii) **Specialisation:** Each partner is expected to contribute to all SMA according to their specific expertise, as related to the project.
- (iii) **Expansion:** Partners are expected to link the SMA with specialised audiences (relevant communities, experts, movements, etc.) they have access to / knowledge of. They will be encouraged to link their own (personal or professional) SMAs to the ones of the project and take advantage of their networks.

In order to ensure that partner's contribution will be consistent, constant, and fair, specific minimum expectations of activity per SMA per partner will be detailed in the Awareness Raising Plan that will be elaborated by M3 (e.g. 1 Facebook post per partner per week). Subsequently the SMA operator (White Research) will monitor the partner's track record and ensure their participation. In addition, partners will agree to contribute with a minimum amount of opinions/articles per year and to a minimum amount of hours of availability per year for interviews, videos, and other promotional material.

3. Specific SMA

3.1 Facebook

In Facebook there is a notable lack of communities and groups with a focus on AD biogas, Community Energy and other related concepts (e.g. Energy Village). After a quick keyword search, no active Facebook Page or Facebook Group related to the above concepts was found. This presents an opportunity for ISABEL as it may be possible to take advantage of this niche and create such a community around the project. The Facebook representation of ISABEL will therefore aim to fill this gap and create a space that:

- ✓ links all other groups and pages associated to relevant and overlapping concepts (including circular economy, bio-based economy, permaculture, industrial ecology, and more); and
- ✓ acts as a news and discussion hub for AD Biogas and Community Energy in general and not ISABEL in particular.

The purpose of the Facebook representation is, therefore, to **build a strong group of followers, beyond ISABEL, and capitalise on the common and overlapping interests of this audience with the project's concepts and activities**. Then, in the context of providing general information, news and developments in concepts and fields related to the project, **the Facebook page will also be used to communicate selected developments and outputs of the project** (e.g. key events, activities, and important achievements).

In order to achieve a continuous flow of information all the partners of the project will be asked to contribute on a regular basis by highlighting relevant news items that come to their attention. In addition specialised online tools will be used to create combined web feeds and RSS feeds that will filter out and deliver on daily basis relevant news, creating a continuously updated news database to help keep the group alive. In order to promote and grow the group, all partners will be asked to “like” it and its posts, participate by posting and commenting, and share it and its posts/discussions with their networks asking their peers to further share in order to spread the word. In order to fulfil the above functions the “**Biogas for the People**” “page” (type: community) was created in Facebook (*note: in the description the affiliation with the project is clearly stated*).

Figure 2: Example of ISABEL Facebook page (the artwork is temporary)

3.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn will be the SMA identity of the project. It will showcase the project, the consortium, and the specific people involved from each partner and provide a link mainly to the community of professionals.

In order to exploit the potential of LinkedIn the project will hold an account as a company and specifically a partnership. This will allow the project's team members to group under the LinkedIn page, provide the possibility for a short description of the consortium and the project, allow the initiation of discussions and posting of news/updates, and finally allow the project to link with existing communities and groups or allow individuals to follow the page and get updated.

Unlike the facebook group, **the LinkedIn page of ISABEL will be project focused.** The integrated newsfeed will consist of content that is either directly related to the project (project updates, progress, events, etc.) or wider developments that are expected to have a direct impact on the project (e.g. changes in regional legislative frameworks). It will therefore often link to the project's website/portal. LinkedIn is also a type of Social Media that favours professional and expert discussions on issues of common interest. This is a function that the project will take advantage as best as possible by initiating such discussions, asking its team members to contribute and attempting to involve followers and 3rd parties from the established LinkedIn group network.

Note that the LinkedIn page cannot be uploaded until the project acquires its own domain name and email accounts. Therefore no screenshot is available at this moment.

3.3 Twitter

Twitter will function as a general dissemination and “heads-up” device covering a broad audience. Through it the project will mostly reproduce and distribute links directing users to other locations (e.g. other SMAs, the portal, etc.) escorted by very short descriptions/announcements to communicate almost everything related to the project: from engagement workshops to participation of project partners to external events and from important milestones to opinion-pieces and articles published in the context of the project. However, twitter will also function the other way around, as a monitoring device of developments and progress in other related EU or national projects and relevant organisations.

Figure 3: Example of ISABEL twitter page (artwork is temporary)

3.4 Youtube

The project has committed to produce at least 10 videos throughout its duration. These may consist of short interviews with partners and/or stakeholders, on-site visits, coverage of project events, etc. **A dedicated Youtube channel will be set up** to collect these videos in a single, easily accessible location. However, the project will go beyond a simple video archive and utilize Youtube's capabilities to further enhance the build-up of a strong online community by establishing connections with relevant channels and producing playlists of relevant videos. The aim will be to maximise visibility of its own videos and use the "comments" as a space for potential feedback and discussion. Since many of the videos will have to be produced locally, in the project's respective regions, the regional partners are expected to contribute towards this task. Furthermore, the help of all partners will be sought in identifying existing relevant videos, building up the playlists, kick-starting the comment section, and share with their peers to maximise dissemination.

Figure 4: Example of ISABEL youtube channel. Artwork is temporary. (screenshot)

3.5 e-Newsletter

The project has committed to produce a **bi-annual e-Newsletter**. This will summarise the project's activities over the last 6 months and will represent an alternative way to inform potential stakeholders while keep existing followers updated. The e-Newsletter, due to its slightly out-dated character, covers a different demographic (in terms of age) than the rest of the (more contemporary) SMAs. It also allows people that are not interested enough in the initial phases of the project, to remain loosely connected and increase their involvement when they feel it is time. Finally, the e-Newsletter functions as an additional tool for measuring the impact of the website. It requires recipients to register in the email list, a process which will take place through a registration form located at the project's portal. This method also provides an additional measure for the project's impact (i.e. number of people registered to receive the newsletter). The SMAs operator will be editor of the newsletter and all partners will contribute with material as required.

3.6 Other

The project will initially deploy the above-mentioned set of SMAs and will dedicate its 'first mile' (M1-M6) to ensure their smooth operation, achieve coordination between partners and make necessary adjustments based on feedback from the embedded analytics. As the project evolves and the SMA bouquet is maturing and streamlined, the needs and requirements will be re-evaluated and additional SMA will be considered. These may include blogs, Flickr, and Slideshare. The latter is particularly relevant to the specific project.

More specifically, **Slideshare** is an online service specialised in storage, display, and distribution of visual (powerpoint) presentations. Since the project has predicted the organisation of several workshops, events, and communication activities, where project partners or third parties will use presentations, a service like Slideshare will be particularly useful in collecting all the material used in one centralised location for ease of access, distribution, and management. An additional advantage of using Slideshare is that it provides an analytics service which allows to monitor the impact of the project's communication strategy. Partners will be provided with the username and password and given direct access and instructions to upload there all the publicly available material.

4. Conclusion

We deploy a wide variety of SMAs with different capabilities and different target audiences to increase the effectiveness of our online communication strategy and complement offline activities as best as possible. However, in addition to this, the use of the specific set of SMAs incurs additional benefits for the project. Specifically, the 5 main tools used (as well as the others that are proposed) embed basic to average analytics capabilities that, combined, allow us to monitor and evaluate the impact of our communication strategy with relative precision. Second, the full bouquet of SMAs integrates written communication abilities (through comments sections etc.) providing various paths for the collection of feedback at different levels (ie general public, specific stakeholders, local communities, and project partners), anonymous or not. In addition, in all of the cases there are functions for the control of postings before they go public from the SMA operator so as to avoid phenomena of trolling, digital vandalism, and association of the project with political or other irrelevant causes.

Although this document outlines the general terms under which the SMAs will operate, the specifics with regard to the partner's roles, the quality and quantity of their contributions, and the finalisation of the overall SMA strategy will be discussed and agreed upon during the kick-off meeting of the project.